

**TRANSFORMATIVE TRENDS: NORTHEAST'S AGRICULTURE RESURGENCE IN FOOD
CROP PRODUCTION AND DIVERSITY**

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Abstract:

This study examines the evolving landscape of crop production in Nagaland, North East, India, through secondary sources, and focuses on the period from 1999-00 to 2014-15. Transformative trends in crop production and diversification in Nagaland were observed. The observations revealed that there was a notably substantial increase in non-cotton fibre crops like jute and Mesta, but a decline in cotton production. Pulses experienced a remarkable growth of 606%. The area under Food Grain cultivation expanded by 51.6%, with a corresponding 128% surge in production, driven by both increased cultivation and improved yields. Rice, the dominant crop occupying 48.5% of cropped area, shows consistent jhum cultivation and amplified Wet Rice Cultivation (WRC) production. Oilseed production exhibits fluctuations, reaching a peak in 2009-10, and later rebounding in 2014-15. These findings offer insights into the dynamic shifts within Nagaland's crop production, vital for informed agricultural policies and interventions aimed at enhancing sustainability and productivity.

Keywords: *Nagaland, India, Crop production, Trends, Food Grain, Rice, Productivity*

1. Introduction:

Agricultural transformation encompasses the process of augmenting farm productivity to establish viable commercial farming practices and fostering interconnections with various sectors of the economy. In the pursuit of agricultural transformation, several critical focal areas demand concentrated attention. North India places considerable importance on agriculture, primarily concentrated in the northern regions of the country, rich in proteins, vitamins, and carbohydrates [1].

In the agricultural context of North-East India, it resides within the Southeast Asia rice domain, with rice serving as the primary food crop [2]. New entrants to the area's agricultural landscape are rubber and diverse varieties of tropical and temperate fruits. An emblematic traditional tree crop cultivated in homesteads rather than in commercially organized plantations is the areca nut. Nevertheless, the region's cultivable land is relatively limited, confined mainly to the alluvial valleys of Assam. Cultivated land constitutes merely 16% of the region's area, and the collective cropped area, incorporating multiple cropping, doesn't surpass 22%. Rice claims dominance over 85% of this cropped expanse [3].

Agricultural production assumes a foundational role across economies, shaping livelihoods and ensuring the food security of myriad individuals. In the context of Nagaland, a northeastern state celebrated for its cultural

diversity and abundant biodiversity, agriculture stands as a cornerstone for sustaining local communities and fostering economic prosperity [4]. The interplay of geographic, climatic, and cultural factors has uniquely moulded Nagaland's agricultural milieu over time.

This study embarks on a comprehensive journey, scrutinizing the trends in crop production within Nagaland. With an expansive repository of secondary data spanning from 1999-00 to 2014-15, the investigation delves into dynamic shifts characterizing the production of significant crop varieties. The potential ramifications of these insights extend to guiding policy formulations, shaping agricultural interventions, and advancing the sustainable growth of Nagaland's agricultural sector. Given the evolving global landscape, comprehending local agricultural nuances is increasingly pivotal, not only for local community prosperity but also for broader regional and national developmental aspirations. Through meticulous scrutiny of crop production trends and correlated factors, this study contributes to the knowledge that will ultimately steer Nagaland's agricultural trajectory. The primary objective of the study is to evaluate the prevailing food production trends in Nagaland, a prominent state in India's Northeast region.

2. Methodology

This study adopted a secondary data analysis-based methodology. This involves gathering and analyzing existing data, information, and research findings from various sources, such as reports, publications, databases, and records of understanding of agricultural production in Nagaland, North East, India, which requires an integration of statistical trends with real-world experiences and perspectives. Secondary data were gathered from two distinct sources given below:

2.1. Land Use Crop Production Statistics for Nagaland, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India: This dataset provided essential production statistics for various crops in Nagaland. The dataset covered the period from 1999-00 to 2014-15, serving as a foundation for analysing crop production trends.

2.2 Statistical Handbooks of Nagaland (2011-2014), Government of Nagaland: These handbooks supplied valuable regional data that contributed to a more holistic understanding of the agricultural landscape in Nagaland.

3. Results

Production data for various crops in Nagaland is available from 1999-00 onwards. This period serves as a baseline for major crop analysis.

Table 1 Change in Production (in %) 1999-00 to 2014-15

Crop category	Production in metric tons (t)		Change in Production (in %)
	1999-00	2014-15	
Food grain	266670	607240	127.7
Rice	222000	454190	104.6
Oilseed	30280	68090	124.9
Pulses	5910	41750	606.4
Spices#	24480	33020	34.9
Sugarcane	30000	189330	531.0
Tuber	44800	130600	191.5
Cotton	350	70	-80.0

Crop category	Production in metric tons (t)		Change in Production (in %)
Fibre (non-cotton)	360	7830	2075.0
Total	378370	1077930	184.9

Notably, as seen in Table 1, there is a remarkable rise in the production of non-cotton fibre crops (jute and Mesta), while cotton production was declining. Pulses have exhibited a noteworthy growth of 606%.

Table 2 Overview of Food Grain Status Area, Production and Yield Wise in Nagaland (1999-00 to 2014-15)

	Maximum	Minimum	Range	Mean	Standard Deviation
Area (ha)	277590	183050	94540	241387	26219
Production (t)	607240	266670	340570	427168	106612
Yield (t/ha)	1.89	1.00	.89	1.44	.21

In Table 2, food grain encompasses rice, wheat, maize, and coarse grains, including millet. The area of Food Grain increased by 51.6% from 1999-00 to 2014-15, while the volume of production surged by 128%, with a 40% yield increase. Both extensification and improved yield contributed to this growth.

Figure 1. Distribution of Food Grain Production (%) across Districts of Nagaland

Figure 1 demonstrates highest cropped area and production for Food grain is in Dimapur, while there is an observed decrease in area and production in the Kohima district. In 2008-2009, three districts of Kiphire, Longleng, and Peren were added to the database due to bifurcation of districts in 2004, and data triangulation could have been an issue.

3.1. Rice Production

Rice dominates 48.5% of the cropped area (195,240 ha in 2014-15). Jhum cultivation area for rice remains consistent at around 95,000 ha. The Wet Rice Cultivation (WRC) area surged by 35% from 70,300 ha (2008-09) to 94,780 ha (2013-14), leading to a 42.4% increase in production. Jhum rice yield remains around 1.8-1.9 t/ha, while WRC yield ranges from 2.45-2.6 t/ha.

Table 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the fluctuations and trends in rice cultivation, production, and yield over the specified period, allowing for a deeper understanding of the dynamics of rice agriculture in Nagaland.

Table 3: Summary of Rice agriculture in Nagaland (1999-00 to 2014-15)

	Maximum	Minimum	Range	Mean	Standard Deviation
Area (ha)	195240	148000	47240	167341	15122
Production (t)	454190	222000	232190	304784	82000
Yield (t/ha)	2.35	1.39	.96	1.80	.33

3.2. Oilseed Production

Table 4 presents the area, production quantity, and yield per hectare for a specific crop within a defined time frame. These metrics offer insights into the variations, averages, and dispersion of key aspects of agricultural production, aiding in understanding the crop's performance and the potential factors influencing it.

Table 4 Summary of Oilseed in Nagaland (1999-00 to 2014-15)

	Maximum	Minimum	Range	Mean	Standard Deviation
Area (ha)	161770	31270	130500	70359	28220
Production (t)	147850	30280	117570	70504	24383
Yield (t/ha)	1.29	.71	.58	.93	.16

4. Discussion

The resurgence of agricultural activity in the Northeast region of India, as highlighted in the context of increased food crop production and diversity, prompts a deeper discussion on the underlying factors, implications, and challenges of this transformative trend. The study's findings offer a comprehensive analysis of the observed trends and their implications, shedding light on the multifaceted dynamics that shape Nagaland's agricultural food crop production. The production data spanning from 1999-00 to 2014-15 reveals significant shifts in crop production dynamics. Notably, the production of non-cotton fibre crops, including jute and Mesta, has experienced a remarkable surge. The overall area has substantially increased, witnessing a 71% growth in gross cropped area, accompanied by increased production for major crop types. However, a decline in yield is noticeable for most crops, except rice, largely attributed to expanded Wet Rice Cultivation (WRC) in the relatively flat terrain of Dimapur district. The proportion of irrigated land remains consistent at around 22%, yet the actual irrigated area has expanded over the years. The impressive growth of 606% in pulse production is a remarkable finding. According to a study (Seitinthang,2014)[5] for the growth of pulses there is a change of 336% in cropped area, a 599 % increase in production, and a mere 10% increase in yield. Rice continues to be a dominant crop, covering almost half of the cropped area. Similarly in a study (Sharma, 2013) [6] the area under crop production has increased (71% increase in gross cropped area) substantially along with the production for the major crop types, however, there is a marked decrease in yield for most of the crops barring rice, which has been mostly due to increased WRC in Dimapur, which is a considerably plain area.

The share of area under irrigation remains constant at about 22%, however, there has been an increase in actual area over the years. There has been a decline in the jhum area for many districts along with the production (Sivakumar et al.,2013) [7]. The fluctuations observed in oilseed production area, and yield are intriguing. Further research (Yano & Lanusosang, 2013) [8] explored the factors such as market demand, weather variations, or policy changes that contribute to these crop production dynamics. The two major oilseeds in the state are mustard/rapeseed and soybean. However, if we refer to the food pattern, soybean is consumed more as a protein food than oilseed by boiling it or fermenting it and using it as a spice (Singh & Daimari, 2013)[1]. Many crops grown in Nagaland, like the Naga Rice Bean, Jobs tear, Chow chow, and Coix seeds, are not included in the national agricultural census. There is a good likelihood that the production of many such crops is not recorded since they are sold in inaccessible marketplaces and consumed in an unrecorded manner. As a concluding thought, it's worth noting that assessing a region's food security requires a thorough familiarity with its local context and food production systems. These foods may be the primary source of vitamins and minerals for the local people, even though many of them are produced and eaten locally without ever entering the market system. (Dikshit & Dikshit, 2014) [9]

In summary of this discussion, Nagaland's agricultural landscape has witnessed shifts in major crop production since 1999-00, with considerable growth in non-fibre crops and pulses. Rice remains pivotal, with both jhum and wet rice cultivation contributing to its output. Oilseed production faced fluctuations, with noticeable variations in area and yield patterns.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the analysis of production data from 1999-00 to 2014-15 in Nagaland unveils significant transforming trends. Notably, non-cotton fibre crops, particularly jute and Mesta, have surged while cotton production declined. Pulses witnessed a remarkable growth of 606%. Food grain production, encompassing rice, wheat, maize, and coarse grains, expanded by 51.6%, with a 128% increase in production and 40% in yield. Rice production, dominating 48.5% of the cropped area, showcased consistent jhum cultivation, contrasted by surging Wet Rice Cultivation (WRC) and yields. Oilseed production displayed fluctuations, peaking at 102,000 ha (2009-10), then rebounding in 2014-15 with a 108% increase, though yield declined by 20%. This data offers insights into Nagaland's dynamic crop production, aiding informed decisions and future interventions.

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